

Green Nanotechnology Techniques, Developing Eco-Friendly Methods for Creating Gold Nanoparticles and Examining their Antiviral Effectiveness against SARS-CoV-2¹

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Abstract

Environmentally-friendly methods are employed to produce gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), as well as to define their properties and apply them in the fight against cancer, including its early detection. Traditional cancer treatments like chemotherapy, radiation therapy, and surgery sometimes fail to affect certain cancer cells. Additionally, these treatments are known to have significant adverse effects and may not always be effective. This underlines the urgency for accelerated progress in research for anti-cancer therapies. Gold is highly favored in nanotechnology because it resists surface oxidation and is chemically inactive. Using green chemistry, nanoparticles are crafted from natural sources, prioritizing ecologically sound practices. Gold nanoparticles are an assembly of gold atoms forming particles that range from 1 to 100 nanometers, gaining remarkable physical, chemical, and optical properties through their minute dimensions and heightened surface area. Storing gold nanoparticles requires careful consideration to preserve their stability and prevent degradation. The antibacterial efficacy of these nanoparticles has been assessed using the agar well diffusion method. Moreover,

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by implementing the broth dilution technique, we can create biocompatible AuNPs with potential applications in biomedicine and other fields where non-toxicity is essential.

Keywords

Green Synthesis, Nanomaterials, Covid, Physical Properties, Gold.

1. Introduction

Nanotechnology refers to the creation and use of objects of different sizes, from 10 to 1000 nanometers. This field combines many scientific disciplines into one broad topic. Nanoparticles, due to their small size and unique shape, have led to much research into their use in biomedicine and the food industry. In today's world, cancer poses a major health problem and is characterized by abnormal and uncontrolled cell growth that varies depending on the cellular state. Scientists and health experts are concerned about the increasing number of cancer patients and people at risk. Developing effective cancer treatment and diagnostic tools remains a challenging task in the medical field. affects the effectiveness of the drug. Additionally, the presence of brain tumors that are resistant to cancer treatments such as antibiotics, radiation, and surgery further complicates the treatment landscape.[5] Additionally, these treatments often cause side effects, and most treatments will too. creates side effects. Negative clinical outcomes show how important it is to accelerate and improve research to prevent cancer [8]. These drugs can successfully treat cancer and destroy cancer cells with a low risk of side effects. Due to their unique effectiveness and safety, nanomedicines for cancer therapy (sometimes called “magic bullets”) are now widely used to treat cancer.

The use of nanoparticles ensures the effectiveness and preservation of anti-cancer drugs, often compared to drug administration guidelines. Efficacy, slow release, long half-life, and reduced toxicity are the main advantages of nanomedicines and their delivery [9]. Since the approval of Doxil Caelyx by the FDA in 1995, the number of cancer-specific nanomedicines has increased significantly. This drug was the first drug used in the treatment of ovarian cancer and HIV-related [7]. Recently, EMA and FDA approved the use of nanotechnology-based cancer therapy. These include Myocet, a liposomal doxorubicin used to treat metastatic breast cancer. Due to their unique physical and chemical properties, gold nanoparticles are thought to be unique cancer treatments.

They are known for their high thermal performance, stability and electricity. By controlling the main components and content, many different products in different shapes and sizes can be produced [12, 13 and 14]. Most nanoparticle (NP) synthesis methods use a bottom-up approach where NPs are composed of simple molecules [15]. One of the best methods for mass production of AuNPs with good sizes and shapes is plant-based green synthesis [16]. The aim of this article is to provide an overview of gold nanoparticles produced using green technologies, their properties and their use in cancer prevention and early diagnosis. The antibiotic properties of AuNPs and their potential mechanisms of action on different strains are discussed based on the literature. Before concluding the article, the main

treatments and problems of AuNP anticancer will be reviewed. Metal nanoparticles have received great attention in optics, cognition, vision, catalysis and biomedical applications [18].

Many theories have been investigated to develop a better method for the synthesis of metal nanoparticles, including some methods such as electrochemical, physical, non-chemical, photochemical and biological. However, due to almost all of these issues and some chemicals, the production cost is very high and the process of improving the quality of the final product is not easy [[19], [20], [21]]. Generally, metal nanoparticles (NPs) are made from noble metals such as silver, gold, platinum, and palladium. Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have attracted attention due to their effective use in sensor development and medical science [22]. The concept of green chemistry is used in the biomedical, pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries to produce different metal nanoparticles. Among these, the use of gold has increased recently. The special quality of gold is its resistance to surface oxidation and chemical inertness, making it suitable for use in nanotechnology and applications. AuNPs have been extensively researched and are currently emerging as important delivery vehicles due to their unique properties such as consistency, easy availability, and non-damaging to cells when using bacteria [17, 19, and 21]. They also have properties such as functionality and good biocompatibility [17, 23]. Studies have also shown that nanoparticles can effectively act as drug carriers for many drugs, including protein, DNA or RNA, small drugs, and other drugs that can be present in the blood for long periods of time. Due to the abundance of natural materials, the synthesis of metal nanoparticles has attracted widespread attention due to their environmentally friendly and inexpensive properties. Various chemicals such as bacteria, yeast, fungi and plant extracts are used in the process. Previous studies have shown that biomolecules, particularly flavonoids, are important for coating nanoparticles and creating nanometer-sized ions. Scientists and researchers around the world have discovered various ethanol plant sites that can be used with different nanoparticles [25, 26]. treatment of cancer has significantly boosted site-effective drug delivery.

Nanoparticles (NPs) made from various plants and their extracts, especially curcumin (CUR), which contains many physiologically active compounds, may be useful in medicine [21 , 27 and 28]. Mountain turmeric (*Curcuma false-Montana* Grah) is an erect plant in the Western Ghats region of Southeast Asia and India and is a member of the Zingiberaceae family [20]. It can be found in damp, shady spots at the edges of damp trees or meadows. It can also be found in deciduous and semi-evergreen forests. Turmeric has long been used in Asia for its medicinal properties, such as treating jaundice, body inflammation, wound healing, liver disease, and blood purification. Many biological methods have been used in the treatment of diseases such as leprosy, cancer, pain, diabetes and heart problems [29]. Previous studies used turmeric essential oil to biosynthesize gold nanoparticles. The produced nanostructures are anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and active against T47D ductal human cancer cells [30]. The existence of CUR is mainly due to the pharmacological properties of turmeric. The rhizomes of some turmeric plants are the source of CUR, a naturally occurring bright yellow diphenolic compound often used as a food additive and colorant. Its medicinal properties include antioxidant, anticancer, antiarthritic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, neuroprotective, cardioprotective and radioprotective effects [31]. Curcumin is considered as an option for the production of green synthetic nanoparticles due to its safety and non-toxicity [32, 33]. Antiviral potential of gold nanoparticles in SARS-CoV-2: Viruses are submicroscopic infectious diseases that replicate only in the brain of an infected person. Bacteria can infect all life forms, from animals and plants to bacteria. They can cause infectious and potentially fatal diseases in humans and other animals [1], [2]. According to recent data, the disease is estimated to cause approximately 2,000,000 deaths worldwide every year (3). Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2.

According to international data, as of January 2020, there are 2,519 confirmed MERS-CoV cases, 866 deaths and a mortality rate of 34.3% [27]. In 2003, the SARS-CoV virus affected 26 countries, causing more than 8,000 confirmed cases [28]. SARS-CoV-2 is the phylogenetic successor of SARS-CoV. Coronaviruses are a group of RNA viruses belonging to the family Coronaviridae of the order Nidoviridae. SARS-CoV-2 was named as the causative agent of COVID-19, which was declared a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. The spread of COVID-19 has led to greater concern about the development of the coronavirus. Vaccines against MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV2 [29], [30]. COVID-19 has been shown to be a highly contagious disease that can spread from person to person through contact or aerosol droplets. Some common symptoms include cough, cold, fever, headache, sore throat, body aches, and loss of appetite. COVID-19 was first reported in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in mid-January 2020. The presence of coronaviruses, including SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, and hCoV-NL63, was confirmed in tears by RTPCR technology.

Permeability Mechanism of SARS-CoV-2:

Viral infection requires an exchange between the virus and the invading virus. Bacteria rely on the cell's machinery to produce proteins; They start with synthesis and then insert the genetic code into the cell where it is copied in the cytoplasm or nucleus. This replication begins almost simultaneously with the production of bacterial RNA and protein. The newly formed bacteria are then incorporated using the infectious agent and released from the host cell.

Specifically, in the case of COVID-19, the SARS-CoV-2 virus is often transmitted through respiratory droplets or aerosols. The patient coughs or sneezes. The patient may show symptoms or simply become infected. Importantly, SARS-CoV-2 can survive on inanimate objects, making it highly contagious. For example, this virus can be effective on metal for several hours or up to three days under certain conditions.

SARS-CoV-2 virus is the RNA virus that causes COVID-19, and its glycoprotein supports its survival in the host. These spikes are important for the initiation of infection. Many studies have proven that this disease is well received in the environment and continues to spread. Additionally, it has acquired genetic mutations that increase its infectivity and survival in the host.

It is important to effectively target the disease in the early stages because inhibitors are more easily accessible from outside the cell. Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) are important in making these bacterial inhibitors. Experiments have shown that gold nanoparticles can protect against human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), influenza, and herpes simplex virus. Bowman et al. It has been shown that gold nanoparticles with high binding capacity can inhibit HIV by blocking the spread of the virus through molecular binding. Studies also show that although gold nanoparticles alone are not sufficient to prevent HIV fusion, their combination with other molecules greatly increases their ability to prevent infection. Figure 1: AuNPs invitro and in vivo studies

The combination of short-length single-stranded DNA with gold nanoparticles leads to the actual formation of easily distinguishable double-stranded DNA. The presence of salt causes the nanoparticles to aggregate and causes a color change from red to blue that can be detected by the naked eye or by transparent UV-visible spectroscopy; this reveals the target SARS nucleic acid depending on the DNA concentration. .

Regarding medical advancement, vaccines represent their ability to improve immunity; Nanoparticles have a special impact in the development of vaccines. Many studies have shown that nanoparticles, including heat exchangers, have a protective effect. For example, in 2011 Staroverov et al. Colloidal gold has been shown to stimulate the immune response against TGEV coronavirus in mice and rabbits, increasing interferon gamma and neutralizing antibodies after vaccination. Additionally, the use of antigen-gold complexes improved T cell numbers and thus the immune response to TGEV compared to the use of antigen alone. Related studies showed that similar complexes also increased levels of IFN, IL-1, and IL-6; This supports the claim that gold nanoparticles are anti-inflammatory agents for injection.

The unique surface plasmons of gold nanoparticles enable wavelength-selective tuning. They have been used to detect MERS-CoV proteins and SARS-CoV antigens by color and can be easily modified by gold-conjugated peptides and reactive antibodies. Using biosensors, 20 nm gold nanoparticles were used to detect SARS-CoV by changing fluorescence in the presence of antibodies specific for the SARS-CoV N protein. Additionally, modification of metal nanoparticles with sulfonate ligands maps the position of acetylheparin sulfate proteoglycan on the cell, making an impact on bacterial adherence and subsequent effects on the bacteria in hand. Recent research shows that gold nanoparticles with sulfonate chains, such as mercaptoethanesulfonate (MES) and undecanesulfonic acid (MUS), cause irreversible changes in various diseases, indicating the potential for the development of Antiviral drugs.

The virus uses cleaved cellular enzymes to enter cells' spike proteins, allowing them to bind to angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2), which has been identified as the primary receptor of SARS-CoV-2. The ACE2 receptor has a key region called lysine 31 that interacts with glutamine 394 of SARS-CoV-2 to initiate its life cycle. Upon binding, the viral envelope fuses with the host cell membrane via the endosomal pathway and releases its RNA into the host cell. The viral protein cleavage enzyme then cleaves the nascent RNA and uses it to synthesize the viral replicase polyproteins pp1a and 1ab. Deficient polymerase activity results in multiple subgenomic mRNAs that are used to produce viral proteins. The Golgi apparatus and endoplasmic reticulum are essential for the transcription of the viral RNA genome and virion proteins. After all the collected bacteria are removed from the cell in the form of vesicles.

1. Synthesis of Gold Nanoparticles:

Gold ions are frequently reduced to their metal forms by capping or stabilizing the species to form gold nanoparticles. There are many methods such as chemical, citrate and seed growth that can be used to produce gold nanoparticles. To make gold nanoparticles, we first used a special type of gold called gold salt. We mix this hot salt with water and make a solution. We then add a substance that helps break down the gold in the solution into smaller particles. This medicine is called a reducer and it works like a "magic" that changes the temperature. We mix the hot solution with the reducing agent by gently stirring. This process causes the gold to dissolve in water and change to form small gold particles [28]. We add another special product called stabilizer to prevent small gold from binding together. The stabilizer acts as a "shield" for the hot particles, keeping them separate and small. After mixing and waiting for a while, the liquid becomes ready for the gold ions to complete their form. As nanoparticles form, the color of the drug changes from a soft yellow to a true red or purple, indicating their formation. Or in other words, mix 20 mL of the bark extract with 10 mm glass tetrachloride in an Erlenmeyer flask at room temperature and statically mix. The color change of the reaction can be seen and the time it takes for it to occur is recorded. When Au/G mangosteen ripens, the color of the drug changes from light brown to dark purple. The final Au-NP nanoparticle emulsion was stored at 4°C. After the reaction was completed, we had to separate the gold nanoparticles from the remaining solution. This can be done using techniques such as fast rotation or using a filter. Finally, we examine gold nanoparticles under powerful microscopes and other devices to examine their size, shape, and other properties. It is worth noting that scientists use more precise methods and techniques in real experiments, but this simple explanation gives you a simple understanding of what gold nanoparticles are like [28, 30, 32].

2. Green Synthesis Process:

Green Synthesis is a process for producing nanoparticles from natural resources using environmentally responsible methods. It tries to lessen the use of dangerous chemicals and their environmental impact. Here is a step-by-step breakdown of how to create nanoparticles using green synthesis: First, scientists choose organic substances from living things like plants, fungi, algae, or biopolymers that have chemicals that can lower metal ions and stabilize nanoparticles. Extracting bioactive components from natural materials is how they prepare them. For instance, water or ethanol are used as solvents for

grinding and extracting plants. The process of creating a metal salt solution involves dissolving a metal salt precursor, such as gold chloride and silver nitrate, in the appropriate solvent, such as water or ethanol. The metal salt solution and the extract are combined. The extract's constituents function as stabilizing and reducing agents. [34]

The metal ions in the solution interact with these substances, reducing them to their metallic state and preventing them from clumping. Under particular temperature and pH restrictions, the mixture is permitted to react. Nanoparticles start to develop and expand during this phase. Once the reaction is complete, the nanoparticles are characterized using techniques like UV-Vis spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, or transmission electron microscopy. These methods assist in identifying the nanoparticles' purity, size, and form. The surplus reactants and contaminants are then taken out of the nanoparticles. Techniques like centrifugation or filtration can be used to accomplish this. The synthesized nanoparticles can be used for various applications, such as medicine, electronics, or catalysis. Further studies can be conducted to explore the properties, stability, and potential toxicity of the nanoparticles. Researchers can also optimize the synthesis conditions to achieve the desired characteristics. [36]

Figure 2 Pictorial presentation of Green synthesis

Gold Nanoparticle Storage (AUNPS):

Gold atoms are arranged in sizes between 1 and 100 nanometers, creating nanomaterials called gold nanoparticles. These nanoparticles stand out with their unique physical, chemical and optical properties due to their size and surface area ratio [38]. When storing gold nanoparticles, many factors need to be taken into account to maintain their stability and prevent degradation. Important information regarding the storage of gold nanoparticles is as follows: Gold: In general, gold nanoparticles are stable at room temperature. However, heat should be avoided. It is recommended to store it between 4°C and 25°C to prevent changes in its physical and chemical properties.

Moisture: Gold nanoparticles are susceptible to oxidation when exposed to moisture. It should be stored in a dry place to avoid unwanted chemicals. Additionally, storing gold nanoparticles in containers or bottles containing a desiccant can help reduce the effect of moisture. **Long-term storage:** Freeze-drying or freeze-drying of gold nanoparticles is recommended for long-term storage. This procedure involves eliminating the sample's water under low pressure and temperature to produce a dry powder that can be kept for a long time. Gold nanoparticles that have been lyophilized should be kept at a temperature of -20°C or below or in the freezer [39].

Light Exposure: Light, especially ultraviolet (UV) light, has the potential to make gold nanoparticles sensitive. Exposure to strong light sources, such as UV rays or direct sunlight, can trigger photochemical processes that result in particle deterioration. Gold nanoparticles should be kept in dark places or covered in aluminum foil to shield them from light exposure and maintain their stability [39, 40].

pH and chemical environment: Extreme pH levels and specific chemicals can make gold nanoparticles vulnerable. They must be kept out of the reach of potent acids, bases, and reactive compounds that might interact with the particles and compromise their stability. They should ideally be kept in a neutral or slightly acidic environment for storage [31].

Contamination: It is advised to handle gold nanoparticles with clean, dry equipment to avoid contamination and the introduction of unwanted particles or substances. Contamination can have an impact on the characteristics and behavior of the nanoparticles [39]. It's crucial to keep in mind that various storage conditions can be required based on the size, shape, surface modifications, and intended applications of the gold nanoparticles. As a result, it is advised that you refer to the supplier's instructions or pertinent scientific literature for detailed instructions for the specific gold nanoparticles you are dealing with.

AuNP Applications and Limitations: Drug delivery systems are technologies designed for the controlled and targeted distribution of drugs. Advances in biomedical engineering have helped us understand the body's resistance to drugs. This represents a major achievement in the fight against cancer because the drug must get to the right place at the right time, in the right concentration, and stay there long enough to be effective. Most methods for targeting cancer cells are unstable, weak, nonselective, and easily disrupted by biochemicals. Therefore, nanotechnology-based drug delivery systems provide an effective drug therapy method for the detection and treatment of cancer [40].

Future research on Gold Nanoparticles (AuNPs)

Future research on gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) should focus on the many issues that continue to evolve towards changing their applications and solving current problems. area. Future research will focus on a variety of topics, including: **Biomedical applications:** Researchers will continue to investigate and develop the use of AuNPs in a variety of biomedical applications, such as drug administration, examination, diagnosis, and treatment. In the future, researchers will work to improve the surface chemistry, functional strategies, and biocompatibility of AuNPs so that they are safe and effective in medicine [41].

Figure 2: Applications of AuNPs

Nanomedicine and Cancer Treatment: There is ongoing interest in utilizing AuNPs for advanced cancer therapies, including photothermal therapy, photodynamic therapy, and combination therapies. Future research may focus on designing multifunctional AuNPs that can precisely target cancer cells, deliver therapeutic agents, and integrate imaging capabilities to improve treatment outcomes [42].

Bio-sensing and Diagnostics: AuNPs have shown promise in bio-sensing applications, including point-of-care diagnostics, disease biomarker detection, and environmental monitoring.

Conclusion

Through vigorous stirring at room temperature with curcumin obtained from *Curcuma pseudomontana* and without the need for other chemicals or outside energy, it was possible to successfully create curcumin-capped gold nanoparticles. The green-produced CUR-AuNPs showed great homogeneity and were roughly 20 nm in size, and numerous spectral studies revealed that they had a remarkable degree of stability. The CUR-AuNPs possessed potent antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities. These experiments suggest that the produced CUR-AuNPs may be appropriate for several biological applications. As a reducing and stabilizing agent, *Jatropha integerrima* Jacq flower extract was employed in the production of nanoparticles. The nanoparticles were found to be spherical and in the 28–43 nm size range by TEM examination. The XRD and SAED patterns were employed to analyze the crystal structure of AuNPs.

The antibacterial activity of the generated nanoparticles was evaluated using the agar-well diffusion method. Using the broth dilution approach, the MICs for *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae* were found to be 5, 10, 2.5, and 2.5 g/mL, respectively. They are a potential therapeutic candidate since these nanoparticles work well against pathogens that are resistant to treatment.

Therefore, biologically produced nanoparticles may potentially have an anti-infective effect and may be added to pharmaceuticals or used topically. Using *G. mangostana* peel extract to make Au-NPs is described in this research as an environmentally beneficial process. The extract demonstrates that the pericarp of *G. mangostana* contains a number of compounds that give the compound its properties as a reducing and stabilizing agent. The possibility of unwanted waste items is increased by using plant peels, and is inexpensive, effective, and secure. There has never been a study that produced Au-NPs using *G. mangos tana*. The prospective applications for the synthetic Au-NPs include biomedical as well as other domains where nontoxicity is significant.

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